

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17829334

Global Orogenesis: Implications For Earthquakes And Tsunamis

¹*Aniebone, V.O., PhD., ²Chukwu-Okeah, G.O., PhD., ³Yusufu, A.K & ⁴Fadipe, A.I

^{1,3,4}Nigerian Institute for Oceanography and Marine Research, Victoria Island, Lagos

²Institute of Niger Delta Studies, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: Aniebone Victor Obiora. Email: aniebonevic@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

An Orogeny is an event that leads to a structural deformation of the Earth's lithosphere (crust and uppermost mantle) as a result of the interaction between tectonic plates. To the geographer orogeny or orogenesis—the formation of mountains. It is brought about by the movements of the rigid plates making up the Earth's crust (described by plate tectonics). Where two plates collide at a destructive margin rocks become folded and lifted to form chains of fold mountains (such as the young fold mountains of the Himalayas). But to field geologists the term orogeny represents a penetrative deformation of the Earth's crust, associated with phases of metamorphism and igneous activity along restricted, commonly linear zones and within a limited time interval. Global orogenesis, the process of mountain building through geological forces and plate tectonics interactions, has significant implications for earthquakes and tsunamis. The implications are loss of lives and infrastructure in earthquake zones of the world. When tectonics plates collide, converge, or diverge, they create complex geological structures that can lead to seismic activity. Various theories that related that have to do orogenesis are the continental drift, seafloor spreading and plate tectonic. All these theories give vital and undeniable proofs to crustal movements that result to earthquake waves and tsunamis that do threaten the human environments causing colossal destruction to lives and infrastructure. Man has no control over the earthquakes and tsunamis, but nevertheless they can be predicted, and with early warning system, possible arrangements can be made for relocation and evacuation. This can minimize losses.

Keywords: Global Orogenesis, Earthquakes, and Tsunamis

INTRODUCTION

According to Gilbert (1890), an orogeny (from the classical Greek *óros* meaning 'mountain' and *genés* meaning 'stemming from') is simply a period of mountain building. An Orogeny is an event that leads to a structural deformation of the Earth's lithosphere (crust and uppermost mantle) as a result of the interaction between tectonic plates. It is the primary mechanism by which mountains are built on continents. In *Orogeny Through Time*, Burg and Ford (1997) claim that: 'To field geologists the term orogeny represents a penetrative deformation of the Earth's crust, associated with phases of metamorphism and igneous activity along restricted, commonly linear zones and within a limited time interval.

Jackson (1997), in what is virtually the bible for English-speaking geologists, wrote: *orogeny* literally, the process of formation of mountains. The term came into use in the middle of the 19th Century, when the

process was thought to include both the deformation of rocks within the mountains, and the creation of the mountainous topography. Only much later was it realized that the two processes were mostly not closely related, either in origin or in time. Today, most geologists regard the formation of mountainous topography as postorogenic. By present geological usage, orogeny is the process by which structures within fold-belt mountainous areas were formed, including thrusting, folding, and faulting in the outer and higher layers, and plastic folding, metamorphism, and plutonism in the inner and deeper layers. The *Hutchin Pocket Dictionary of Geography* (1993) has the following entry:

Orogeny or orogenesis—the formation of mountains. It is brought about by the movements of the rigid plates making up the Earth's crust (described by plate tectonics). Where two plates collide at a destructive margin rocks become folded and lifted to form chains of fold mountains (such as the young fold mountains of the Himalayas).

Global orogenesis, the process of mountain building through geological forces and plate tectonics interactions, has significant implications for earthquakes and tsunamis. When tectonics plates collide, converge, or diverge, they create complex geological structures that can lead to seismic activity.

OROGENS THROUGH GEOLOGIC TIME

The Earth is about 4,500 million years old. The old rocks are known as Precambrian, and are normally devoid of fossils. For the past 560 million years life has been abundant and fossils are common in sedimentary rocks. This stretch of time is known as the Phanerozoic. The Phanerozoic is divided into units of various types. A division into three Eras separates the Palaeozoic (old life), the Mesozoic (middle life) and the Cenozoic (recent life, also known as the Cainozoic). These three main groups are divided into smaller groups called Periods. The Cenozoic is frequently divided into the Quaternary—the uppermost Period—and the Tertiary. It is also sometimes found convenient to split the Cenozoic into the Palaeogene, which includes the Paleocene, Eocene and Oligocene, and the Neogene, which includes the Miocene, Pliocene and Pleistocene. The Quaternary is split into the Pleistocene, and the Recent (the last 10,000 years). A geological time-scale is shown in Figure 1. In general we know more of recent events in Earth history than of remote times, in our landscapes recent events have more impact than remote ones, and the more recent tectonics are visible at the surface while ancient tectonic features may be preserved in rocks but not in landscapes. We thus have a perspective of time, with a clearer view and larger scale for those features near us in time, and a more limited view of events and features in the distant, remote past. Sometimes ages are given in years. This is usually in millions of years, which may be indicated by Myr or Ma. Ages determined by isotopic methods are often called absolute ages, but perhaps numerical ages is a better term.

ERA	PERIOD	EPOCH	M. yrs ago	
PHANEROZOIC	CAINOZOIC	QUATERNARY	Recent - about 10,000 yrs	
		TERTIARY	NEOGENE	Pleistocene
	PALAEOGENE		Miocene	5
			Oligocene	24
			Eocene	37
			Paleocene	58
	MESOZOIC	CRETACEOUS		65
		JURASSIC		141
		TRIASSIC		205
	PALAEOZOIC	PERMIAN		251
		CARBONIFEROUS		298
		DEVONIAN		354
		SILURIAN		410
		ORDIVICIAN		434
PRECAMBRIAN	CAMBRIAN		490	
	PROTEROZOIC		545	
	ARCHAEAN		2500	
	HADEAN		4000	
AGE OF EARTH			4600	

Figure 1. Geological time scale. Ages are as currently used by the Australian Geological Survey Organisation.

However our increasing understanding of the rheology of lithospheres allows geologists today to view orogenesis on a larger scale as the interaction of a series of geodynamic processes (Burg and Ford (1997). In particular, is there a change in style or mode of orogeny through geological time, or is variety of orogenic features rather reflecting different rheologies and boundary conditions in space. Figure 2 shows the global distribution of orogenies of different ages

Figure. 2. World map of orogens distinguished by their age. 1, Archaean orogens of Choukroune et al. a, Dharwar craton and b, Superior province; 2, Mount Isa Terrain, O'Dea et al; 3, the Scandinavian Caledonides, Milnes et al. and Rey et al. 4, the Lachlan fold belt, Gray; 5, the Urals, Puchkov; 6, the Variscides, Rey et al.; 7, the Central Andes, Lamb et al. Adapted from Miyashiro et al. (1979) and Condie (1982).

THEORIES RELATED TO OROGENESIS. CONTINENTAL DRIFT

According to the theory of continental drift, the world was made up of a single continent through most of geologic time. That continent eventually separated and drifted apart, forming into the seven continents we have today. The first comprehensive theory of continental drift was suggested by the German meteorologist Alfred Wegener in 1912. The hypothesis asserts that the continents consist of lighter rocks that rest on heavier crustal material—similar to the manner in which icebergs float on water. Wegener contended that the relative positions of the continents are not rigidly fixed but are slowly moving—at a rate of about one yard per century. In Wegener’s day the concept of drift could be supported by evidence from the distribution of plants and animals, the distribution of fossils, ancient deserts and glaciated rocks, and by matching other geological evidence. Wegener also thought that the mountains along the Pacific coast of the Americas were pushed up at the front edge of drifting continents where the continental slab buckled against the Pacific. In 1958 Carey showed that the ‘fit’ of the South Atlantic was remarkably good, within half a degree over 45 degrees of latitude, which could hardly be accidental, and by 1965 Bullard and others showed that the entire Atlantic could be closed to give an equally good fit.

SEA FLOOR SPREADING

Seafloor spreading was later demonstrated in all the oceans, though the Pacific ridge is not in the centre of the ocean, but runs into the continents of North and South America. Ocean surveys in the nineteenth century showed that the Atlantic was shallowest along the centre. A mid-Atlantic ridge runs the full length of the Atlantic and remains very close to the middle, emerging above sea level in Iceland. The greatest geological discovery of this century is that the ocean floors are spreading. Magnetic studies showed a symmetry about the mid-Atlantic ridge, and later studies showed that the sea floor gets consistently older with distance from the ridge. New seafloor is being created at the spreading sites, and old seafloor migrates away from them. There is overwhelming evidence that the Atlantic Ocean has been formed by the drifting apart of the continents that bound it. The sea floor grows at the centre—the mid-Atlantic rift—and spreads sideways. It seems that the Atlantic Ocean only started to open in the Triassic, about 200 million years ago.

But if all the oceans are growing, they must disappear somewhere, unless the Earth is increasing in size. The sites where ocean disappears are called ‘subduction sites’, and are located at island arcs and ‘active’ continental margins. The driving force is thought to be convection currents, rising at the spreading sites and sinking at subduction sites.

PLATE TECTONIC

According to the plate-tectonics theory scientists believe that Earth's surface is broken into a number of shifting slabs or plates, which average about 50 miles in thickness. These plates move relative to one another above a hotter, deeper, more mobile zone (a slippery layer of the mantle called the asthenosphere) at average rates as great as a few inches per year. The driving force is thought to be convection currents, rising at the spreading sites and sinking at subduction sites (see figure 3). Most of the world's active volcanoes are located along or near the boundaries between shifting plates and are called plate-boundary volcanoes. The peripheral areas of the Pacific Ocean Basin, containing the boundaries of several plates, are dotted with many active volcanoes that form the so-called Ring of Fire. The Ring provides excellent examples of plate-boundary volcanoes, including Mount St. Helens. However, some active volcanoes are not associated with plate boundaries, and many of these so-called intra-plate volcanoes form roughly linear chains in the interior of some oceanic plates. The Hawaiian Islands provide perhaps the best example of an intra-plate volcanic chain, developed by the northwest-moving Pacific plate passing over an inferred “hot spot” that initiates the magma-generation and volcano-formation process.

Plate tectonics differs in having the oceans as part of the system. Seafloor is created at spreading sites, and destroyed at subduction sites. If a spreading site were to originate beneath a continental area, the continent would be rifted and drifted apart and a new ocean basin formed in the middle.

THE THEORY OF PLATE TECTONICS

Figure 3. The processes of plate tectonics (Source: Gabrielarogers.blogspot.com)

PLATE-TECTONICS THEORY—THE LITHOSPHERE PLATES OF EARTH AND OROGENIC PROCESSES

Plate tectonics is a name for the concept that the earth's crust can be divided into several plates (about 20 tectonic plates). Volcanoes and earthquakes tend to cluster around interacting plate boundaries, The Pacific Ring of Fire is the best known example of this correlation. The figure 4 shows the boundaries of lithosphere plates that are active at present. The world's main tectonic features are related to activity at the edges of the plates. New crust is created at spreading sites, and old crust is destroyed. The double lines indicate zones of spreading from which plates are moving apart (constructive plate boundary) The lines with barbs show zones of underthrusting (subduction), where one plate is sliding beneath another. The barbs on the lines indicate the overriding plate (destructive plate boundary). The single line defines a strike-slip fault along which plates are sliding horizontally past one another (transform fault boundary). The stippled areas indicate a part of a continent, exclusive of that along a plate boundary, which is undergoing active extensional, compressional, or strike-slip faulting at subduction zones. For the past 30 years plate tectonics has been the ruling theory in geology, and has been used to account for almost everything in Earth Science. Plate tectonics was first described by J.T Wilson in 1965 and was applied to orogeny a year later by Wilson. He made it clear that orogeny resulted from convergent plate motion, but important sideways motion along orogenic belts was also believed to be an integral part of orogenic processes. Investigation of orogenic belts along cross sections revealed that there are large number of types of orogenic belts. The four main types are: transpressional, subduction-controlled, obduction-controlled and collision-controlled. See the appendixes for the various types of plate boundaries

Formation of an orogen is accomplished in part by the tectonic processes of subduction (where a continent rides forcefully over an oceanic plates (noncollisional orogens) or convergence of two or more continents (collisional orogens) (Frank 2003). However, usually no continental crust is subducted, only uplifted example the Alps. Orogeny usually produces long arcuate structures known as orogenic belts, which consist of long parallel strips of rock with similar characteristics along the length of the belt. Orogenic belts are associated with subduction zones which consume crust, produce volcanoes and build island arcs. The arcuate structure is attributed to the rigidity of the descending plate, and island arc cusps relate to tears in the descending lithosphere (Gerald et al. 2001)

An orogenic event may be studied: (1) as a tectonic structural activity. (2) As a geographical event and (3) As a chronological event.

Orogenic events:

- (a). Cause distinctive structural phenomena related to tectonic activity.
- (b). Affect rocks and crust in particular regions, and
- (c). Happen within a specific period.

Zwart (1967) proposed three types of orogenic belts based principally on the amount of ophiolites, high-pressure metamorphic rocks and granites. The three types are: (1). Hercynotype (back-arc basin type) (2). Alpinotype (ocean trench type) (3). Cordilleran (arc) type. Many phenomena follow plate boundaries. Shallow earthquakes follow the line of the sub-oceanic ridges, the spreading sites. Deep earthquakes follow the line of subduction sites around the Pacific rim and lines of deep sea trenches. A few earthquakes follow the rift valleys which might be incipient spreading sites. Some of them are explained below:

Figure 4 Tectonic plates. The map depicts the ‘plates’ of plate tectonics, each bounded by lines of spreading or subduction. (Source: U.S. Geological Survey)

CRUSTAL ACTIVITIES AT VARIOUS BOUNDARIES SUBDUCTION SITES

Subduction sites (known also as collision sites and active margins) provide more varied tectonic settings than spreading sites, including the following types. Some of the possible effects are shown in Figure 5

CONTINENT-CONTINENT COLLISIONS (HIMALAYAN TYPE)

The most spectacular example of this collision type is that presumed to have occurred between India and continental Asia. The idea is that India broke away from the supercontinent of Gondwana, drifted north, and was subducted under Asia, causing the rise of the Himalayan and the Tibet Plateau.

The collision of Africa with Europe is another example of the plate tectonic explanation of mountains, especially in Europe.

CONTINENT-OCEAN COLLISION

This is the commonest sort of collision envisaged in the plate tectonic theory, but can itself be divided into two.

SIMPLE SUBDUCTION (ANDES TYPE)

This is allegedly typified by the plate junction on the west side of South America.

The Pacific Ocean is said to be subducted under the South American continent. This is supposed to account for:

- the deep trench along the edge of the continent;
- the rise of the Andes;
- the volcanic activity of the Andes;
- the granite plutons of the Andes.

ISLAND ARC SUBDUCTION

Around the western edge of the Pacific the map shows many islands arranged in festoons of arcs, either single lines or double rows of islands, making a quite clear pattern of curves. These lie some distance off the continent, and in front they have a deep trench very like that off the coast of South America. These deeps also bound a Benioff zone dipping towards the continent and marked by earthquakes reaching depths of several hundred kilometers. Sometimes sediments are scraped off the down-going slab and thrust on to the continent, perhaps to form 'fold mountains' (Figure 5d). Some arcs face east (Indonesian arc), some arcs have no continent behind them (South Sandwich Islands), and some lines of islands have all the attributes of arcs such as Benioff zones and trenches but lack the arcuate shape (Solomon Islands). Nevertheless the island arc complex makes one of the distinctive landform and tectonic assemblages of the Earth and, despite many complexities and variations, island arcs mark plate junctions

OBDUCTION

In a few collision zones a slab of ocean floor is thought to have over-ridden rather than under-ridden the continent. In Papua New Guinea a slab of basic rocks with petrology, layering and structures exactly like those thought to be typical of ocean

a. Continent-continent collision (Himalayan type)

b. Continent-ocean collision with buckling up of the continent and subduction of the ocean floor (Andes type)

c. Obduction of the sea floor over the continent with later isostatic rise to form mountains (Cyprus type)

d. Thrusting of sediments on to the continental plate with foreland folding at the front (Appalachian)

e. Thrusting of sediment under the continent, where they might melt and form granite.

f. Crustal thickening resulting from plate collision, possibly accompanied by gravity sliding of rocks near the surface (Pyrenees type).

Figure 5. Some possible mechanisms for creation of mountains by plate tectonics

(By Cliff Ollier and Colin Pain, 2000)

crust makes the mountainous terrain of the Papuan Ultramafic Belt. Another arc is the Troodos Mountains of Cyprus where dyke-ridden oceanic rocks override continental rocks. 'Obduction' is the term for this overriding, in contrast to subduction when the oceanic slab goes down below the continental mass. The commonest mountains in island arcs are volcanoes, but some arcs have mountains made of bedrock, usually as fault block mountains. Alternatively, sediment may be carried under the continent (Figure 5e) where it is presumed to melt and form granite, or perhaps melt and provide the magma for volcanoes along the collision zone.

OCEAN-OCEAN COLLISION

An arc may be formed, as in the South Sandwich Islands (Scotia arc) where a strip of spreading Pacific seems to be pushing a finger of oceanic crust into the oceanic crust of the Atlantic. The contact is marked by a trench, earthquake zone and active volcanicity. The Caribbean arc is somewhat similar, with the Pacific pushing into the Atlantic. The arcs may have sufficient elevation to cause mountains. The curvature of the Indonesian arc may result partly from the Pacific Ocean spreading into the Indian Ocean.

CRUSTAL THICKENING

In this hypothesis the collision of two plates causes a thickening of the crust, resulting in uplift, and perhaps sediments slide off the uplifted axis (Figure 5f).

OROGENIC CYCLE

The sequence of repeated cycles of sedimentation, deposition and erosion, followed by burial and metamorphism, and then by formation of granitic batholiths and tectonic uplift to form mountain chains is called the orogenic cycle (David, 2004).

Orogeny involves plate tectonics, and the forces result in a variety of associated phenomena, including magmatism, metamorphism, crustal melting, and crustal thickening. What happens in a particular orogen depends upon the strength and rheology of the continental lithosphere, and how these properties change

during orogenesis. An orogeny once formed is subject to some other processes such as erosion and sedimentation.

KEY IMPLICATIONS OF OROGENESIS ON EARTHQUAKES

There are implications of orogenesis on earthquakes and some of them are discussed hereunder.

(a) Seismic Activity: Orogenesis causes rocks to deform and fracture, giving rise to fault zones and complex fault networks that can produce earthquakes. The San Andreas Fault in California being a notable example of a fault zone associated with the Pacific-North American plate boundary.

(b) Earthquake Patterns: Different types of orogenesis, such as subduction-related orogenesis, can result to distinct earthquake patterns. For example, subduction zones are characterized by frequent and powerful earthquakes, as seen in the Indonesian subduction zone where the Indo-Australian Plate is being subducted beneath the Eurasian Plate.

(c) Volcanic Activity: Orogenesis can also lead to volcanic activity, which can sometimes indicate impending earthquakes. The Andes mountain range is a prime example of volcanic activity resulting from subduction related orogenesis.

(d) Crustal Deformation: Orogenesis involves crustal thickening, folding, and faulting, which can lead to significant earthquakes. The Himalayas, formed due to the collision between Plates, are a classic example of crustal deformation resulting from orogenesis.

EXAMPLES OF OROGENESIS – RELATED EARTHQUAKES

(a). Cascadia Subduction Zone: This zone is prone to large-magnitude earthquakes due to the subduction of Juan de Fuca plate beneath the North American plate.

(b). Japanese Subduction Zone: The subduction of the Pacific Plate beneath the Eurasian Plates creates a complex network of faults and fractures, leading to frequent and powerful earthquakes.

(d). Andean Mountain Building: The subduction of the Nazca Plate beneath the South American Plate has resulted in the formation of the Andes mountain range and associated seismic activity. The table 1 below shows the recent and near recent earthquake and tsunamis.

RECENT AND NEAR RECENT EARTQUAKES AND TSUNAMIS (Source: Climatecosmos.com)

YEAR	LOCATION	MAGNITUDE	EFFECT/CHARACTERISTICS
2011	Tohoku, Japan	9.1 Richter	One of the most powerful earthquakes in Japan’s history. It triggered a massive tsunami causing widespread destruction and a nuclear crisis
2004	Indian Ocean, Indonesia	9.1-9.3 Richter	This undersea earthquake triggered a devastating tsunami, including Thailand, Sri Lanka, India, and Somalia, resulting in over 230,000 deaths
2024	Philippines	6.5 Richter	It struck Mindanao, triggering landslides and damaging infrastructure
2024	Fiji	7.3 Richter	A deep focus magnitude shook Fiji Islands, triggering tsunami warnings
2024	Japan	6.9 Richter	It struck Kyushu, triggering landslides and minor injuries
2025	Papua New Guinea	7.1 Richter	It struck near Kimbe, causing limited casualties

2025	Chile	6.8 Richter	It shook Valparaiso, prompting brief evacuations
2025	Kamchatka, Russia	8.8 Richter	It struck off Russia's Kamchatka Peninsula triggering tsunamis alerts across the Pacific, including Japan, Canada, parts of the U.S

CONCLUSION

There are two types of crust:

(a) Continental crust which is older, thicker and less dense. (b) Oceanic crust which is younger thinner and denser.

There are three directions of movements between plates. (1) Converging: Where two plates are moving towards each other. (2) Diverging: Where two plates are moving away from each other. (3) Passive: Where two plates are moving side by side.

There are six different combinations of types crust and directions of movements

Destructive - Where oceanic and continental crust converge

Destructive – Where oceanic and oceanic crust converge

Destructive (collision) – Where continental and continental crust converge

Constructive – Where two plates diverge under the ocean

Constructive – Where continental crust is diverging

Constructive – Where two plates move parallel to each other. The appendixes show the various plate margin and boundaries.

From a geodynamic point of view, orogenesis encompasses all processes that result in crustal thickening, causing uplift and hence high topography. By present geological usage, orogeny is the process by which structures within fold-belt mountainous areas were formed, including thrusting, folding, and faulting in the outer and higher layers, and plastic folding, metamorphism, and plutonism in the inner and deeper layers.

Plate tectonics is the main agent of orogenesis. Orogeny resulted from convergent plate motion, but important sideways motion along orogenic belts was also believed to be an integral part of orogenic processes. Mountain complexes result from irregular successions of tectonic responses due to sea-floor spreading, shifting lithosphere plates, transform faults, and colliding, coupled and uncoupled continental margins. Formation of an orogen is accomplished in part by the tectonic processes of subduction (where a continent rides forcefully over an oceanic plates (noncollisional orogens) or convergence of two or more continents (collisional orogens) (Frank 2003). The processes of orogeny can take tens of millions of years and build mountains from plains or from the seabed. Orogeny usually produces long arcuate structures known as orogenic belts. Orogenic belts are associated with subduction zones which consume crust, produce volcanoes and build island arcs. Global orogenesis, the process of mountain building through geological forces and plate tectonics interactions, has significant implications for earthquakes and tsunamis. The implications are loss of lives and infrastructure in earthquake zones of the world.

REFERENCES

- Bullard, E., Everett, J.E. and Smith, A.G. (1965). The fit of the continents around the Atlantic. *Phil. Trans. R Soc. A.*, 258, 41–51.
- Burg, J.-P. & Ford, M. (eds), (1997), *Orogeny through Time*, Geological Society Special Publication No. 121, pp. 1-17.
- Carey, S.W. (1958). *The Tectonic Approach to Continental Drift. Continental Drift: A Symposium*. Geol. Dept., Univ. Tasmania, Hobart.
- Condie, K. C. (1982). *Plate tectonics and crustal evolution*. Pergamon Press.

David, J. (2004). The orogenic cycle. The geology of Australia. Cambridge University Press. P.48
 Gilbert, G. K. (1890). Lake Bonneville. US Geological Survey Monographs, 1.
 Hutchinson, *Pocket Dictionary of Geography* (1993). Helican, Oxford.
 Jackson, J.A. (1997). *Glossary of Geology*. 4th edn. American Geological Institute, Alexandria, Virginia
 Miyashiro, A., Aki, K. & Sengor, A. M. C. (1982). Orogeny. John Wiley & Sons.
 Ollier, C.D. and Pain, C.F. (2000). The Origin of Mountains. Taylor & Francis e-Library, London and New York
 The Theory of plate tectonics. <http://www.gabrielarogers.blogspot.com/images>. Retrieved: 24th March, 2017.
 Zwart, H. J. (1967). The duality of orogenic belts. *Geologie en Mijnbouw*, 46,283-309.

APPENDIXES

Appendix 1. Various plate boundaries showing the geologic features.

BOUNDARY	PLATE ACTION	DIAGRAM	EFFECTS (Geologic Features)
Convergent	Collide together → ←		Mountains, Volcanoes, <u>OR</u> Volcanic islands
Divergent	Move apart ← →		Mid-ocean Ridges (sea mountains) <u>OR</u> Ocean basins <u>OR</u> Rift valleys
Transform	Slide past each other ↗ ↖		Earthquakes

Appendix 2. Types of Plate Margins

Type of Margin	Divergent	Convergent	Transform
Motion	Spreading	Subduction	Lateral sliding
Effect	Constructive (oceanic lithosphere created)	Destructive (oceanic lithosphere destroyed)	Conservative (lithosphere neither created or destroyed)
Topography	Ridge/Rift	Trench	No major effect
Volcanic activity?	Yes	Yes	No

Appendix 3. The Plate Boundaries

Lithosphere thickens away from the axis.

(a) At a divergent boundary, two plates move away from the axis of a mid-ocean ridge. New oceanic lithosphere forms.

The process of consuming a plate is called subduction.

(b) At a convergent boundary, two plates move toward each other; the downgoing plate sinks beneath the overriding plate.

No new plate forms, and no old plate is consumed.

(c) At a transform boundary, two plates slide past each other on a vertical fault surface.

Appendix 4. Types of crusts and crustal movements

